

TRANSFORM

Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility

*Report of the deliberative process conducted
within the EU H2020 TRANSFORM project.*

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Authors:

Cecilia Gaballo (Giannino Bassetti Foundation)
Anna Pellizzone (Giannino Bassetti Foundation)
Angela Simone (Giannino Bassetti Foundation)

Graphics:

formicablu srl

Photos:

Tommaso Correale Santacroce (Giannino Bassetti Foundation)

www.transform-project.eu

www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/it/iniziative/transform-eu

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TRANSFORM

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti
for Responsibility in Innovation

Regione
Lombardia

FINLOMBARDA
FINANZIAMO SVILUPPO

Abstract

The report aims to illustrate the first Citizens' Jury conducted in Italy on Responsible (data-driven) Smart Mobility. In June 2022, 24 people residing in Lombardy Region gathered in Milan to learn, discuss and form recommendations to be delivered to Lombardy Region in order to make regional policies on these issues more responsible and inclusive. The Jury took place within the framework of TRANSFORM, a project funded by the European Commission and coordinated by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation, to involve citizens in decisions on research and innovation in three European regions (Lombardy in Italy, Catalonia in Spain, Brussels-Capital Region in Belgium).

Milan, July 2022

Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility

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Introduction

To foster mobility development aligned with the needs and characteristics of the territory, Lombardy Region drew up the 'Smart Mobility and AI' strategy in 2020. To build a shared vision and plan activities, the Lombardy government consulted regional players active in the sector – such as research institutions, companies, and civil society organisations – and identified four priority action areas, including 'connectivity and data'. The digitalisation of mobility and the collection of information on citizens' movements make it possible to plan and manage transport and mobility services in a new and efficient way, but not without social and ethical implications, e.g., in terms of privacy, inclusiveness of the most vulnerable, and accessibility. The Citizens' Jury, organised in Lombardy as part of the TRANSFORM project coordinated by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation, was held to identify responsibility-related issues linked to smart (data-driven) mobility directly from the voice of citizens. The final aim of the **Citizens' Jury** was to provide Lombardy Region with recommendations to develop services in this area that are as close as possible to citizens' expectations, needs, and values.

The model: Citizens' Jury

Citizens' Juries are one of the possible ways in which deliberative processes are carried out – i.e., those processes in which a group of citizens meets, learns, discusses, and elaborates collective recommendations on a specific issue of common interest to be delivered to the decision-makers who commissioned the deliberative process itself. For the citizens – selected so that the group reflects the characteristics of the target population (*mini-public*), for example, in terms of age, gender, and area of residence – this is a great responsibility, but also a great opportunity to make their voices heard and, at the same time, to represent the community they belong to and its different needs. Therefore, everyone should have the same chance to participate, and the selection should ideally take place randomly.

The Citizens' Jury of the TRANSFORM project

In the case of the EU TRANSFORM project, the jurors met for two full days, on the 11th and 25th of June 2022, from 9.30 am to 5.30 pm. The discussion took place in

plenaries and breakout sessions and was conducted by professional facilitators. The first day was entirely dedicated to the informative phase, thanks also to the participation of some experts to whom citizens could address their questions. The second day focused on the discussion phase, aimed at identifying responsibility issues and possible social impacts of data-driven smart mobility, and on the deliberation phase, which consisted in elaborating the actual recommendations and delivering them to the Region.

The jurors of the TRANSFORM project

Twenty-four citizens attended the Jury on the first day and 22 on the second. All of them were over 18 and resided in Lombardy. The 22 citizens who gathered for the second day had also taken part in the first one. The sample was balanced by gender, age, and province of residence. The selected group was also mixed in terms of other socio-demographic factors, such as income and educational qualification, to ensure a diversity of voices, experiences and points of view, which are needed to implement deliberative initiatives properly.

The experts

Five experts participated in the information day. During the first informative session, Francesco Lescai, Associate Professor in Bioinformatics at the University of Pavia, provided an overview of **Big Data and AI**. Francesca De Chiara, Policy Leader Fellow at the European University Institute in Florence, introduced the topic of **Open Data**. In the second informative moment, Professor Gianpiero Mastinu, Professor of Vehicle Construction at the Politecnico of Milan and Secretary General of the Lombardy Mobility Cluster, described some technological features of smart mobility. In the last part of the discussion with the experts, Gabriele Suffia – an expert in privacy in the context of Smart-Cities and currently a Ph.D. student in Science, Law, and Technology at the University of Bologna – spoke about **privacy and techno surveillance**. Arda Lelo, lecturer in architectural history, co-founder, and vice-president of the think tank Period, fostered a reflection on the issues of **inclusion and gender equity** in smart mobility policy design.

The organisers, the commissioning public authority, and the funder

The Jury was organised by Giannino Bassetti Foundation – a Milan-based civil society organisation involved in responsible innovation for almost 30 years and coordinator of TRANSFORM – in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda. The recipient of the recommendations (and the commissioning public authority) is the Directorate General for Education, Universities, Research, Innovation, and Simplification of Lombardy Region. Bassetti Foundation outsourced participants recruiting process to Istituto Piepoli, which also partially supported the facilitation. The TRANSFORM project, within which the Citizens' Jury takes place, is funded by the European Commission within the H2020 Framework Programme.

The program

First day, 11th June

The jurors met for the first time on the 11th of June, and the day was dedicated to:

- Presenting the TRANSFORM project and the Jury (by Giannino Bassetti Foundation)
- Introducing the policies and activities of Lombardy Region on smart mobility (by Lombardy Region)
- Describing the Lombardy Region's E015 platform, which collects various types of data and makes it available to everyone to develop new services for citizens and businesses (by E015)
- Giving citizens the chance to dialogue with five experts on data, mobility, and related responsibility issues, such as open data, privacy, and gender and mobility data (information phase).

For the complete agenda of the first day, see Appendix I.

Second day, 25th June

The second day of the Jury took place on the 25th of June and was devoted to:

- Identifying – at first – the issues of responsibility to be taken into account when drafting the recommendations (in other words: elements of attention to which the recommendations must respond)
- Drafting and refining the recommendations
- Delivering the recommendations to Lombardy Region.

For the complete agenda of the second day, see Appendix II.

The results

The responsibility issues

During the morning of the first day, citizens identified responsibility issues related to developing data-driven mobility services. The discussion took place in three groups, starting with the presentation of eight 'cards', each representing present and future data-driven mobility service (e.g., smart traffic lights, smart parking, on-demand bus – see Appendix III for the full set of cards). The results were then presented in plenary (22 people). Below are the responsibility issues identified by the citizens:

1. Privacy (data collection, use, and sharing, and techno-sur-

veillance)

2. Profiling (collection and automated processing of personal data to cluster individuals into categories based on their behaviour)
3. Inclusiveness: territorial inclusiveness and for disadvantaged groups
4. Economic accessibility (protection of economically disadvantaged groups) and digital (protection of the digitally non-literate)
5. Need to provide information (on the existence and functioning of services)
6. Security (safety and cybersecurity).

Recommendations

In the second phase, starting from the responsibility themes, citizens elaborated and refined recommendations, which were finally approved unanimously.

For each theme, the recommendations were organised into 1) objectives and 2) measures that contribute to the achievement of each objective.

Digital accessibility

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region for a user-friendly and motivating system

to access transport services that everyone can use, even those who are not accustomed to technology.

MEASURES:

- Provide economic incentives as part of the system itself, such as discounts on tickets or longer ticket duration, to encourage the use of the system
- Provide separate interfaces: a basic one for non-digital users and a more complex one with more options and services for those who are able to use it; also provide for a gradual evolution of the service as the user becomes familiar with the system
- Do not advertise or link external services to avoid confusing citizens
- Create services that are accessible to everyone, including people with disabilities or difficulties in using technology (e.g., blind people who cannot read monitors)
- Inform citizens on the existence of the transport access system through the Region's channels and through the ticket itself.
- Economic accessibility

Economic accessibility

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region that the mobility services it finances

do not lead to differences between social classes, becoming services for the few and that the possibility of paying in several ways, not only electronically, is guaranteed for people who cannot or do not want to use their payment cards on digital devices,

MEASURES:

- Provide the possibility of recharging the digital money box for mobility services by using apps, token, or retailers.
- Provide economic incentives to use digital payment (ticket discounts).

Cybersecurity

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to safeguard the protection of the personal data of the users of data-driven mobility services and to ensure the smooth functioning of the technology behind the mobility services.

MEASURES:

- Reassure citizens by providing them with information on how the security of personal data underlying data-driven mobility services is guaranteed
- Reassure citizens of the safety standards of the technologies

used for the mobility services, informing them on how and when maintenance is carried out (e.g. smart traffic lights)

- Inform citizens of any problem occurred when the service is operating and having backup units in case of breakdown (e.g., smart traffic lights)
- Ensure that there is an interconnection of digital mobility services with the police, allowing anonymous geolocation in case of an emergency and need for intervention
- Provide alert systems in the apps underlying data-driven mobility services in case of account and data breaches.

Privacy

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to ensure proper management of the data that citizens provide for data-driven mobility services.

MEASURES:

- Ensure compliance with the GDPR
- Inform citizens that data is used by service providers financed by Lombardy Region only for the stated purposes
- Provide 'precise' information on the purpose of data processing

(who uses it, for which purpose, for how long, in case of withdrawal what happens to the data)

- Provide information to citizens on anonymization procedures (making them available on the Region's app or site)
- Provide information to citizens on what they can do if there is a violation of the GDPR
- Provide clarity on the consent given by citizens and the possibility of revoking consent without constraints.

Profiling

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to ensure clarity and transparency with regard to the profiling of users of data-driven mobility services.

MEASURES:

- Guarantee the information necessary to make all citizens aware of the consequences of their virtuous or negative behaviour, in terms of profiling and providing information on which public authorities have access to profiling data
- Provide the possibility of excluding profiling in the case of apps with rewards, guaranteeing

access to basic functions, even without profiling

- Guarantee the possibility of deleting citizens' data without withdrawal.

Territorial inclusivity

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to formulate a data-driven integrated regional transport plan, adapted to the current needs of territorial inclusion.

MEASURES:

- Provide a system to interconnect data from public services, as a basis of an efficient regional intermodal mobility system, in which all useful information can be collected and made available to citizens throughout Lombardy (i.e., not only in large cities) via apps, panels, modems, or other systems.

Architectural inclusivity

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to ensure that all citizens with specific needs have access to all the information they need to use data-driven mobility services.

MEASURES:

- Standardise the protocols of transport companies and infrastructures at local and regional

level to provide data and information not only on the means of transport itself (timetables, connections, delays), but also on the possibility of boarding public transport with one's own means of transport (e.g., scooter) or aids (e.g., wheelchair for the disabled).

Economic inclusivity

OBJECTIVE: We ask Lombardy Region to guarantee that people from all social classes can access mobility services.

MEASURES:

- Ensure economic inclusion by standardising the price of tickets of local companies at regional level and making it easy to apply for subsidized tickets at regional level.

Information inclusivity

OBJECTIVE: We ask the Lombardy Region to make all services accessible also to citizens who are not digitally literate.

MEASURES:

- Set up Digital education programmes for people that are digitally non-literate
- Implement information services (e.g., on GDPR) through social entities, schools, or others.

Delivery and take-over by Lombardy Region

In the final part of the second day, the recommendations of the citizens, formulated and unanimously approved by the Jury, were formally handed over to the commissioning public authority, Lombardy Region. Three representatives of the jurors read out the recommendations in the presence of two representatives of the regional administration. Lombardy Region committed to taking citizens' ideas and suggestions into account in its future actions in the area of smart mobility and, should it not be possible to incorporate them (for example, in the case of requests that do not fall within the remit of the regional authority), to explain the reasons for this.

Appendix I – Agenda of the first day

Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility

EU H2020 TRANSFORM Project Milan, 11th June 2022

10.00 - 10.30 Welcome Coffee

10.30 - 11.15 Introduction to the project and to the agenda of the day

Angela Simone - EU H2020 TRANSFORM Project Coordinator, *Giannino Bassetti Foundation*

Enza Cristofaro - DG Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification, Lombardy Region

Damiano Apicella - Technical Management Board, E015

11.15 - 11.30 Coffee Break

11.30 - 13.00 Experts presentations – In-group formulation and plenary question space

Francesco Lescai – Associate Professor in Bioinformatics, University of Pavia

Francesca De Chiara - Policy Leader Fellow, European University Institute

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

14.00 - 15.15 Expert presentation – In-group formulation and plenary question space

Gianpiero Mastinu - Full Professor of Vehicle Construction, Politecnico of Milano - Secretary General, Lombardy Mobility Cluster

15.15 - 15.30 Coffee break

15.30 - 17.00 Experts presentations – In-group formulation and plenary question space

Arda Lelo - Lecturer in architectural history – Co-founder and Vice President, *Period think tank*

Gabriele Suffia - Privacy expert in the context of Smart-Cities – Ph.D. candidate in Science, Law and Technology, University of Bologna

17.00 - 17.20 Plenary discussion on any topics citizens wish to study further

17.20 - 17.30 Conclusion of the day and greetings

Appendix II – Agenda of the second day

Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility

EU H2020 TRANSFORM Project Milan, 25th June 2022

10.00 - 10.30 Welcome coffee

10.30 - 11.10 Introduction to the agenda of the day - **Angela Simone** (*Giannino Bassetti Foundation*)

11.10 - 13.00 Dialogue phase – plenary and groups (it includes coffee break)

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

14.00 - 15.50 Deliberation phase I – plenary and groups

15.50 - 16.00 Coffee break

16.00 - 17.00 Deliberation phase II – plenary and groups

17.00 -17.20 Presentation of collective recommendations to Lombardy Region representatives

17.20 - 17.30 Next steps and closing greetings - **Angela Simone** (*Giannino Bassetti Foundation*)

Appendix III – Cards

MAPPING OF ELECTRIC CHARGING STATIONS (FOR VEHICLES)

WHICH DATA?

Positioning data of electric vehicles charging stations and geolocation data of the electric vehicle

COLLECTED HOW?

Geolocation of the vehicle/positioning of the moving citizen to activate the service on the vehicle's mobile phone or on-board computer through a specific app

WHAT IS IT USED FOR?

To find the electric recharging stations nearest to one's position

and possibly calculate the distance and shortest route to reach it

WHO NEEDS IT?

Citizens using an electric vehicle

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

In areas where there is network coverage.

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SMART TRAFFIC LIGHT

WHAT DATA?

Real-time vehicle flow data

COLLECTED HOW?

Through sensors on the traffic lights

WHAT DOES IT DO?

It makes traffic flow smoother

WHO NEEDS IT?

Users moving on the roads where the traffic lights are placed; PAs to better manage traffic flows

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

At particularly congested traffic junctions in the city.

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MAPPING CITIZENS' MOVEMENTS

WHAT DATA?

Travel data (travel time, vehicle used, route) for a specific time window. The data do not identify the individual citizen

COLLECTED HOW?

Through geolocation of the citizen who downloads a specific app on his mobile phone and input of other data by the citizen (on the type of vehicle used)

WHAT IS IT USED FOR?

To understand the mobility flows of citizens in a certain geographical area and the type of vehicles used in order to better plan mobility services

WHO NEEDS IT?

PAs and companies that need to understand mobility flows and plan better services, and, ultimately, citizens. Citizens who volunteer themselves to data collection can receive discounts and rewards in return

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

In areas where there is a need to understand better travel flows and good network coverage, and the average potential user has a good digital disposition.

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ON-DEMAND BUS

WHAT DATA?

User data (departure and arrival position of those who need to travel, specific needs due to disability) and data related to small buses (geolocation, arrival time of the bus, journey time, and any other data related to the service, such as free seats).

COLLECTED HOW?

By the user: entered by the citizen through an app on the phone, via registration, through which the ride is paid for

WHAT IS IT USED FOR?

To make public transport services more efficient, reduce traffic, reduce costs of underused buses.

WHO DOES IT SERVE?

Citizens who need to travel in a specific area; PA to reduce public transport costs, environmental costs, etc.

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

In defined areas where travel is more concentrated.

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INTELLIGENT PARKING

WHAT DATA?

Data from vehicles entering and leaving the car park, both to identify the number of vehicles present and to identify the specific vehicle (license plate number)

COLLECTED HOW?

Through sensors placed in structures at the entrance and exit of the car parking area or on the car park road surface

WHAT IS IT USED FOR?

To find out the availability of parking spaces in real-time in a car park either providing this information on panels placed on roads and other

visible places close to the parking area or on an app, through which you can also reserve a parking space for a specific date and duration. Specific categories (people with disabilities, 'pink parkings') may have reserved or facilitated parking spaces in the location

WHO NEEDS IT?

The citizen on the move who needs a parking space or the citizen who plans in advance to move and use it

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

In any car park but especially in car parks that are particularly used in specific areas of the city

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DIALOGUE BETWEEN MEANS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT

WHAT DATA?

Real-time data on public transport movements (e.g., arrival/delay times of buses and trains)

COLLECTED HOW?

Through geolocation systems using GPS

WHAT IS IT USED FOR?

To provide real-time information to passengers who need to make a connection through the use of monitors placed on public transport (e.g., on the bus or the train) or through apps

WHO NEEDS IT?

Passengers who use public transport and who travel using several means of transport (intermodal mobility) and need to quickly assess which routes are best suited to their needs

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

Wherever there are connections between different public means of transport, especially for heavily used intermodal routes.

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DIGITAL IDENTITY FOR VEHICLES

WHAT DATA?

Data linked to vehicle characteristics: registration number, type of vehicle (e.g., car, ambulance), environmental class, etc.; data produced by the vehicle in operation: geo-referencing, speed, consumption, etc.

COLLECTED HOW?

Data linked to the vehicle's characteristics 'at birth' are collected by creating a digital identity mirroring that of real vehicles; data produced by the vehicle in operation are collected via the on-board computer and transmitted online

WHAT DOES IT DO?

It puts the vehicle in dialogue with infrastructures (to pay motorway tolls or to open gates for emergency vehicles, etc.), with other objects that have a digital identity (e.g., to communicate with other vehicles and with

mobile phones of passengers in sharing systems, etc.) or with service providers (to transmit and receive traffic information, etc.).

WHO NEEDS IT?

The citizen who uses that vehicle (whether the owner or in a sharing system); other users interested in the movements of that vehicle (other drivers in traffic, etc.); all parties interested in monitoring traffic and vehicle behavior (PA, motorway networks, traffic police, insurance companies, etc.). Private companies and PAs can introduce reward systems (discounts on tolls, etc.), preferential taxation or specific marketing (customised policies, etc.) for virtuous behavior (little use, low speed, etc.).

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

Where there is internet coverage; where there are other digital objects with which the vehicle can communicate.

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VIRTUOUS CITIZENS IN MOBILITY, REWARDED CITIZENS

WHAT DATA?

Data on virtuous behaviours (e.g., use of public transport or sharing), including data retrieved through geolocation services.

COLLECTED HOW?

Collected by citizens downloading an app that, using a gaming system, can earn points to reach certain thresholds that entitle the users to rewards, discounts (in shops affiliated with the initiative) and concessions (e.g., on utility bills or public transport subscriptions)

WHAT DOES IT DO?

Incentivises virtuous mobility behaviour

WHO NEEDS IT?

The PA to promote virtuous mobility behaviour, and the "virtuous" citizens to receive rewards and discounts for their behaviour

WHERE CAN IT BE USED?

In areas (e.g., cities) where the PA and private individuals work together to encourage virtuous mobility behaviours.

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For more information, please contact:

Angela Simone
angela.simone@fondazionebassetti.org

Anna Pellizzone
anna.pellizzone@fondazionebassetti.org

Cecilia Gaballo
cecilia.gaballo@fondazionebassetti.org

@FGBassetti
[@TRANSFORM_eu](https://www.instagram.com/TRANSFORM_eu)

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